

TRANSLATION IN FASHION AND THE ART OF DRESSING

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Abstract: This paper discusses the theoretical and methodological issues of translating fashion words and expressions and compares these with the expectations and perceptions of students

Results indicate that when analyzing the translation of the fashionable terminology of glossy magazines, it is noticed that for most of the terms translators do not find equivalents in Russian and use tracing and transcription, especially for shoe designs. It is assumed that it is for this sense of communication in global simplicity. We can conclude that a large layer of vocabulary is translated by tracing, transliteration of transcription in the absence of an equivalent in the target language.

Key words: fashion industry, clothing design, equivalent, methods of translation, tracing, transcription, transliteration

1. Introduction

The fashion industry plays a significant role in influencing society. Thanks to fashion, public opinion is being formed. This circumstance is due to the direct position of the fashion industry in the system of social institutions and the limited access of the audience to the information circulating in it. Delivery of information about current events, new collections and trends of the season is carried out thanks to the media, acting as a kind of filter of news facts.

It should be pointed out what happened in the fashion industry in the second half of the 20th century. Almost all fashion houses were located in Europe and with the outbreak of World War II either closed or moved to the United States. It was there that the designers continued to create. It was in the USA that a new mass production of clothes was opened and developed, new types of fabrics were invented (for example, nylon - nylon), new styles and directions of malls (street fashion - street

1. Examples of the most recognizable terms in the field of clothing design and fashion can be such as: prayer, manskin, catwalk, runway, and even a thread with a needle. These words are words that are understandable to a native.

2. Methods

When reviewing various articles in fashion magazines, it was noticed that some lexical units that entered the Russian language in the first third - mid-twentieth centuries .

Also, when analyzing the translation of the fashionable terminology of glossy magazines, we noticed that for most of the terms translators do not find equivalents in Russian and use tracing and transcription, especially for shoe designs. It is assumed that it is for this sense of communication in global simplicity. For example, on the Internet. It will be easier for users of the Instagram platform to achieve mutual understanding, as well as to save speech means.

The section of footwear terminology is of the greatest interest in translation, since world famous brands, competing with each other, create new footwear models almost every month. And therefore, in the communication of a modern person, a tendency has appeared to use, instead of words denoting varieties of shoes, the names of brands adapted to Russian speech:

"Найки", "канверсы" (Converse), "Vans", "бэлэнсы" (New balance). Лабутены (Christian Louboutin), Угги (UGG), Timba, Timberland Company, etc. In these examples, several translation techniques are used, such as transcription and transliteration in combination with tracing.

3. Perceived outcomes

Besides in the course of our research, an internet survey was also carried out 213 respondents of different age and gender and education answered the questions on the topic "Do you know the terms of the mole?"

It was found that 52% of respondents do not know the listed terms, 27% know the terms but do not give a definition, 17% know the terms and partially give definitions, and only 4% know the terms and definitions. It was found that young people from 17 to 23 are most knowledgeable in this topic, and people aged 45 have little command of the presented vocabulary.

Therefore, with regard to the research practice itself, one can draw the following important conclusion: before starting translation, it is important to understand for which audience the translation is being performed. Because for the youth target audience, for example, speaking of flesh color nude, it is not necessary to translate literally or translate in principle. But if the translator translates for a more mature target audience, whose representatives find it more difficult to adapt foreign words in their speech, then you need to translate with the explanations: nude - a color that has flesh tints.

4. Conclusion

So, we can conclude that a large layer of vocabulary is translated by tracing, transliteration of transcription in the absence of an equivalent in the target language. Subsequently, the language is replenished with borrowed vocabulary, which, on the one hand, has a positive effect on the volume of the lexicon of the language, but on the other hand, the abundance of foreign words projects misunderstanding in the communication of representatives of different target audiences. For this reason, an additional descriptive active stock of the language. most of the items require special attention for further implementation.

Based on the practice of research into the features of translation of terms in the field of fashion, the main conclusions were also made:

1. The main principle of this research work is the term conveyed by the term.
2. To adequately present the content of the lexical unit. The translator requires knowledge of not only Russian terminology, but also English, having previously studied all the components of this unit.

3. At present, a bilingual dictionary is not always trusted source. For an adequate translation, the translator requires certain skills in working with such lexical units and knowledge of the appropriate methodology.
4. Most of the texts on fashion are written in a journalistic style with artistic elements; in this kind of texts, in contrast to the texts of the scientific style, some terms, especially the native ones for the English language, are recognized more corporeally, metaphorical terms are often used. which also complicates the translation process. Therefore, the translator must first isolate such lexical units from the general language ones and, accordingly, determine the methods of their translation.
5. If there is no equivalent term in the translation language in the scientific text, the translator borrows it or creates a new one, or also adds a terminological meaning to the general language unit.
6. Today the problem of translation is urgent. The difficulties of translation are related to traditions with differences in culture and language

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